

Metal carbonyls: 18 electron rule, electron count of mononuclear, polynuclear and substituted metal carbonyls of 3d series. General methods of preparation (direct combination, reductive carbonylation, thermal and photochemical decomposition) of mono and binuclear carbonyls of 3d series. Structures of mononuclear and binuclear carbonyls of Cr, Mn, Fe, Co and Ni using VBT. π -acceptor behavior of CO (MO diagram of CO to be discussed), synergic effect and use of IR data to explain extent of back bonding.

Zeise's salt: preparation and structure, evidences of synergic effect and comparison of synergic effect with that in carbonyls.

Metal Alkyls: Important structural features of methyl lithium (tetramer) and trialkyl aluminium (dimer), concept of multicentre bonding in these compounds. Role of triethylaluminium in polymerization of ethane (Ziegler-Natta Catalyst). Species present in ether solution of Grignard reagent and their structures, Schlenk equilibrium.

Ferrocene: Preparation and reactions (acetylation, alkylation, metallation, Mannich condensation). Structure and aromaticity. Comparison of aromaticity and reactivity with that of benzene.

Types of Ligand

π - Bonding

π -Donor ligands decrease Δ_o whereas π -acceptor ligands increase Δ_o ; the spectrochemical series is largely a consequence of the effects of π bonding when such bonding is feasible.

A **π -donor** ligand is a ligand that, before any bonding is considered, has filled orbitals of π symmetry around the M-L axis. Such ligands include Cl^- , Br^- , OH^- , O^{2-} and even H_2O .

The energies of the full π orbitals on the ligands will not normally be higher than their σ -donor orbitals (HOMO) and must therefore also be lower in energy than the metal d orbitals. Because the full π orbitals of π donor ligands lie lower in energy than the partially filled d orbitals of the metal, when they form molecular orbitals with the metal t_{2g} orbitals, the bonding combination lies lower than the ligand orbitals and the antibonding combination lies above the energy of the d orbitals of the free metal atom (Fig.). The electrons supplied by the ligand π orbitals occupy and fill the bonding combinations, leaving the electrons originally in the d orbitals of the central metal atom to occupy the antibonding t_{2g} orbitals. The net effect is that the previously nonbonding metal t_{2g} orbitals become antibonding and hence are raised closer in energy to the antibonding e_g orbitals. It follows that π -donor ligands decrease Δ_o .

Fig. A) The effect of π bonding on the ligand-field splitting parameter. Ligands that act as π donors decrease Δ_o . Only the π orbitals of the ligand are shown. B) Ligands that act as π acceptors increase Δ_o . Only the π orbitals of the ligand are shown.

A **π -acceptor** ligand is a ligand that has empty π orbitals that are available for occupation.

Typically, the π -acceptor orbitals are vacant antibonding orbitals on the ligand (usually the LUMO), as in CO and N₂, which are higher in energy than the metal d orbitals. The two π^* orbitals of CO, for instance, have their largest amplitude on the C atom and have the correct symmetry for overlap with the metal t_{2g} orbitals, so CO can act as a π -acceptor ligand.

Because the π -acceptor orbitals on most ligands are higher in energy than the metal d orbitals, they form molecular orbitals in which the bonding t_{2g} combinations are largely of metal d-orbital character (Fig. 20.21). These bonding combinations lie lower in energy than the d orbitals themselves. The net result is that π -acceptors increase Δ_0 .

Representative ligands that match these classes are

π donor	weak π donor	no π effects	π acceptor
I ⁻ , Br ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , F ⁻	H ₂ O	NH ₃	PR ₃ , CO

Zeise's salt: preparation and structure, evidences of synergic effect and comparison of synergic effect with that in carbonyls.

Preparation

Alkenes are routinely found bound to metal centres: the first organometallic compound isolated, Zeise's salt, was a complex of ethene. Alkenes normally bond side-on to a metal atom with both carbon atoms of the double bond equidistant from the metal with the other groups on the alkene approximately perpendicular to the plane of the metal atom and the two carbon atoms.

In this arrangement, the electron density of the C=C π bond can be donated to an empty orbital on the metal atom to form a σ bond. In parallel with this interaction, a filled metal d orbital can donate electron density back to the empty π^* orbitals of the alkene to form a π bond. This description is called the Dewar-Chatt-Duncanson model (Fig. 1) and η^2 -alkenes are considered to be two-electron neutral ligands.

Fig. 1. The interaction of ethene with a metal atom. (a) Donation of electron density from the filled π molecular orbital of ethene to a vacant metal σ orbital. (b) Acceptance of electron density from a filled $d\pi$ orbital into the vacant π^* orbital of ethene.

Electron donor and acceptor character appear to be fairly evenly balanced in most ethene complexes of the d metals, but the degree of donation and backdonation can be altered by substituents on the metal atom and on the alkene. When the π backbonding from the metal atom increases, the strength of the C=C bond decreases as the electron density is located in the C=C antibonding orbital and the structure tends to that of a C-C singly bonded structure, a metallocyclopropane:

Dihaptoalkenes with only a small degree of electron donation from the metal have their substituents bent slightly away from the metal atom, and the C=C bond length is only slightly greater than in the free alkene (134 pm). When the degree of backdonation is greater, substituents on the alkene are bent away more from the metal atom and the C-C bond length approaches that characteristic of a single bond. Steric constraints can also force the other groups on the alkene to bend away from the metal atom.

The electron-withdrawing substituents on the olefin, by lowering the energy level of the π^* orbital, favor backbonding and the metallacyclopropanic structure. Thus the tetracyanoethylene complexes much more often have this structure than the parent ethylene complexes. Also, in the metal-olefin structure, the σ bond from the olefin to the metal, weakly compensated by the π^* backbonding, creates a fraction of positive charge on the carbon atoms, which renders them more susceptible to attack by the nucleophiles. In the olefin complexes depicted as metallacyclopropanes, the four substituents are out of the “olefin ligand plane” and point behind

Carbon monoxide

Carbon monoxide is a very common ligand in organometallic chemistry, where it is known as the carbonyl group. Carbon monoxide is particularly good at stabilizing very low oxidation states, with many compounds (such as $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$) having the metal in its zero oxidation state.

A simple picture of the bonding of CO to a metal atom is to treat the lone pair on the carbon atom as a Lewis σ base (an electron-pair donor) and the empty CO antibonding orbital as a Lewis π acid (an electron-pair acceptor), which accepts π -electron density from the filled d orbitals on the metal atom. In this picture, the bonding can be considered to be made up of two parts: a σ bond from the ligand to the metal atom and a π bond from the metal atom to the ligand. This type of π bonding is sometimes referred to as backbonding.

Carbon monoxide is not appreciably nucleophilic, which suggests that σ bonding to a d-metal atom is weak. As many d-metal carbonyl compounds are very stable, we can also infer that π backbonding is strong and the stability of carbonyl complexes arises mainly from the π -acceptor properties of CO. Further evidence for this view comes from the observation that stable carbonyl complexes exist only for metals that have filled d orbitals of an energy suitable for donation to the CO antibonding orbital. For instance, elements in the s and p blocks do not form stable carbonyl complexes. However, the bonding of CO to a d metal atom is best regarded as a synergistic (that is, mutually enhancing) outcome of both σ and π bonding: the π backbonding from the metal to the CO increases the electron density on the CO, which in turn increases the ability of the CO to form a σ bond to the metal atom.

Molecular orbital for CO

The molecular orbital energy level diagram for carbon monoxide have 2s and 2p orbitals on both the atoms that can participate in the formation of σ and π orbitals. The energy level diagram is shown in Fig. 1. The ground-state configuration is

A more formal description of the bonding can be derived from the molecular orbital scheme for CO (Fig. 3), which shows that the HOMO has σ symmetry and is essentially a lobe that projects away from the C atom. When CO acts as a ligand, this 3σ orbital serves as a very weak donor to a metal atom, and forms a σ bond with the central metal atom. The LUMOs of CO are the π^* orbitals. These two orbitals play a crucial role because they can overlap with metal d orbitals that have local π symmetry (such as the t_{2g} orbitals in an O_h complex). The π interaction leads to the delocalization of electrons from filled d orbitals on the metal atom into the empty π^* orbitals on the CO ligands, so the ligand also acts as a π acceptor.

Fig. The molecular orbital scheme for CO shows that the HOMO has σ symmetry and is essentially a lobe that projects away from the C atom. The LUMO has π symmetry.

One important consequence of this bonding scheme is the effect on the strength of the CO triple bond: the stronger the metal-carbon bond becomes through pushing electron density from the metal atom into the π bond, the weaker the CO bond becomes, as this electron density enters a CO antibonding orbital. In the extreme case, when two electrons are fully donated by the metal atom, a formal metal-carbon double bond is formed; because the two electrons occupy a CO antibonding orbital, this donation results in a decrease in the bond order of the CO to 2.

In practice, the bonding is somewhere between $M-C=O$, with no backbonding, and $M=C=O$, with complete backbonding. Infrared spectroscopy is a very convenient method of assessing the extent of π bonding; the CO stretch is clearly identifiable as it is both strong and normally clear of all other absorptions. In CO gas, the absorption for the triple bond is at 2143 cm^{-1} , whereas a typical metal carbonyl complex has a stretching mode in the range $2100 - 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Carbonyl stretching frequencies are often used to determine the order of acceptor or donor strengths for the other ligands present in a complex. The basis of the approach is that the CO stretching frequency is decreased when it serves as a π acceptor. However, as other π acceptors in the same complex compete for the d electrons of the metal atom, they cause the CO frequency to increase. This behaviour is opposite to that observed with donor ligands, which cause the CO stretching frequency to decrease as they supply electrons to the metal atom and hence, indirectly, to the CO π^* orbitals. Thus, strong σ -donor ligands attached to a metal carbonyl and a formal negative charge on a metal carbonyl anion both result in slightly greater CO bond lengths and significantly lower CO stretching frequencies.

Carbon monoxide is versatile as a ligand because, as well as the terminal bonding mode, it can bridge two or three metal atoms.

The CO stretching frequencies generally follow the order $MCO > M_2CO > M_3CO$, which suggests an increasing occupation of the π^* orbital as the CO molecule bonds to more metal atoms and more electron density from the metals enters the CO π^* orbitals. As a rule of thumb, carbonyls bridging two metal atoms typically have stretching bands in the range $1900-1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and those that bridge three atoms have stretching bands in the range $1800-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ the formal charge on iron is -5, and in $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$ the formal charge on chromium is -6. We should expect that the back donation would be more extensive in either of these compounds than it is in the case of $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$. Because the greater back donation results in a greater reduction in C-O bond order, the infrared spectra of these compounds should show this effect. The positions of the CO stretching bands for these compounds are as follows:

$\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$	2057 cm^{-1}
$\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$	2034 cm^{-1}
$\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$	1981 cm^{-1}

Further changes in C-O stretching vibrations occur when other ligands are present. For example, the CO stretching band in $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$ is found at 2100 cm^{-1} , whereas that in $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{CO})_3$ is found at approximately 1900 cm^{-1} . The structure of the latter compound is

In this case, the product is the fac isomer, in which all NH_3 ligands are trans to the CO molecules. Ammonia does not form π bonds to metals because it has no orbitals of suitable energy to accept electron density. Thus, the back donation from Cr in $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{CO})_3$ goes to only three CO molecules, and the bond order is reduced even more than it is in $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$, where back donation occurs equally to six CO molecules. There is, of course, an increase in Cr – C bond order and stretching frequency in $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{CO})_3$ compared to $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$. Based on the study of many mixed carbonyl complexes, it is possible to compare the ability of various ligands to accept back donation

Bonding of Octahedral complex

Figure 1 shows the energy levels that arise when a strong-field ligand such as carbon monoxide bonds to a d-metal atom. Carbon monoxide is a strong-field ligand, even though it is a poor σ donor, because it can use its empty π^* orbitals to act as a good π acceptor.

The energy level diagram shows six bonding MOs that result from the ligand-metal σ interactions, and three bonding MOs that result from π interactions. Thus up to 18 electrons can be accommodated in the nine bonding MOs.

An indication of the size of the HOMO-LUMO gap (Δ_0) can be gained from a consideration of its lack of colour, which results from a lack of any electronic transitions in the visible region of the spectrum, that is Δ_0 is so large that such transitions are shifted to the UV.

The only way to accommodate more than 18 valence electrons in an octahedral complex with strong-field ligands is to use an antibonding orbital. As a result, such complexes are unstable, being particularly prone to electron loss and acting as reducing agents. Compounds with fewer than 18 electrons will not necessarily be very unstable, but such complexes will find it energetically favourable to acquire extra electrons by reaction and so populate their bonding MOs fully.

The bonding characteristic of the carbonyl ligand is replicated with other ligands, which are often poor σ donors but good π acceptors. Hence, octahedral organometallic compounds are most stable when they have a total of 18 valence electrons around their central metal ion.

Fig. 1 The energy levels of the d orbitals of an octahedral complex with strong-field ligands.

Note: In an octahedral (Oh) environment, the orbitals of the central metal atom divide by symmetry into four sets

Metal orbital	Symmetry label	Degeneracy
s	a_{1g}	1
p_x, p_y, p_z	t_{1u}	3
$d_{x^2-y^2}, d_{z^2}$	e_g	2
d_{xy}, d_{yz}, d_{zx}	t_{2g}	3

Fig. The π overlap that may occur between a ligand p orbital perpendicular to the M-L axis and a metal d_{xy} orbital.

Both methods of electron counting are illustrated for the following complexes.

Complex	Method A		Method B	
$[\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$	Fe(II)	6 e ⁻	Fe	8 e ⁻
	2 CO	4 e ⁻	2 CO	4 e ⁻
	4 CN ⁻	8 e ⁻	4 CN ⁻	4 e ⁻
	2 - charge	^a		2 e ⁻
		<hr/> 18 e ⁻		<hr/> 18 e ⁻
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Fe}$ (ferrocene)	Fe(II)	6 e ⁻	Fe	8 e ⁻
	2 $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5^-$	12 e ⁻	2 $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$	10 e ⁻
		<hr/> 18 e ⁻		<hr/> 18 e ⁻
$[\text{Re}(\text{CO})_5(\text{PF}_3)]^+$	Re(I)	6 e ⁻	Re	7 e ⁻
	5 CO	10 e ⁻	5 CO	10 e ⁻
	PF ₃	2 e ⁻	PF ₃	2 e ⁻
	+ charge	^a	+ charge	-1 e ⁻
		<hr/> 18 e ⁻		<hr/> 18 e ⁻

^aCharge on ion is accounted for in assignment of oxidation state to Re.

Determine the valence electron counts for the metals in the following, not all of which are 18-electron complexes.

- $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$
- $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ni}(\text{NO})$ (has linear Ni-N-O)
- cis*-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂
- W(CH₃)₆

Identify the first-row transition metal for the following 18-electron species.

- $[\text{M}(\text{CO})_3(\text{PPh}_3)]^-$
- HM(CO)₅
- $(\eta^4\text{-C}_8\text{H}_8)\text{M}(\text{CO})_3$
- $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{M}(\text{CO})_3]_2$ (assume single M-M bond)

What charge, z , would be necessary for the following to obey the 18-electron rule?

- a. $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)_2\text{Ru}]^z$
- b. $[\text{Co}(\text{CO})_3(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})]^z$
- c. $[\text{NiCl}(\text{PF}_3)_3]^z$

Determine the specified quantity.

- a. The metal–metal bond order in $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2]$
- b. The expected charge on $[\text{W}(\text{CO})_5(\text{SnPh}_3)]^z$
- c. The identity of the second-row transition metal in the 16-electron complex $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\eta^1\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5)(\eta^3\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5)_2\text{M}$
- d. The number of CO ligands in $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{W}(\text{CO})_x]_2$, which has a tungsten–tungsten triple bond
- e. The number of CO ligands in $\text{Mn}(\text{CO})_x\text{Cl}$

Examples of Donor and Acceptor Ligands.

σ Donor	π Donor ^a	π Acceptor ^a
NH_3	OH^-	CO
H_2O	Cl^-	CN^-
H^-	RCO_2^-	PR_3

^aThese ligands also act as σ donors.

Metal Alkyls: Important structural features of methyl lithium (tetramer) and trialkyl aluminium(dimer), concept of multicentre bonding in these compounds. Role of triethylaluminium in polymerization of ethane (Ziegler-Natta Catalyst). Species present in ether solution of Grignard reagent and their structures, Schlenk equilibrium.

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Methyl lithium (tetramer)

A great deal of effort has been directed to determining the structures of lithium alkyls. It has been determined that in hydrocarbon solutions the dominant species is a hexamer when the alkyl groups are small. In the solid phase, the structure is body-centered cubic with the $(\text{LiCH}_3)_4$ units at each lattice site. Each unit is a tetramer in which the four lithium atoms reside at the corners of a tetrahedron and the methyl groups are located above the centers of the triangular faces. The carbon atoms of the alkyl groups are bound to the three lithium atoms at the corners of the triangle. This structure is shown in **Figure 1**.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 1 The structure of the tetramer of methyllithium. Only two of the four methyl groups are shown.

FIGURE 2 Orbital overlap leading to the formation of a two electron three center bond in $[\text{Li}(\text{CH}_3)_4]$.

Bonding of the methyl group to three lithium atoms involves an sp^3 orbital on the methyl group simultaneously overlapping three orbitals (they may be 2s or hybrids of 2s and 2p orbitals) on the Li atoms. This can be shown as illustrated in **Figure 2**. Although this picture of the bonding in methyllithium is generally adequate, it is probably an oversimplification of the true situation. Three-center two-electron bonds exist in numerous types of compounds (such as diborane), but it may be in this case that there is also some weak interaction between the lithium atoms.

Trialkyl aluminium(dimer)

The structure of $[\text{Al}(\text{CH}_3)_3]_2$ is shown in **Figure 1**. In this case, an orbital on the methyl group overlaps with orbitals on two aluminum atoms to give three-center two-electron bonds. Although there are four bonds to each aluminum atom, the orientation of the bonds deviates considerably from typical tetrahedral cases. Because the distance between the aluminum atoms is relatively short, there may be some partial bonding between them. Note that the angle between the bonds to the two terminal CH_3 groups is quite close to that corresponding to sp^2 hybrid orbitals on the aluminum atoms. This would leave p orbitals available to form a σ bond between the aluminum atoms. It should also be noted that the $\text{Al}-\text{C}_t$ bonds are considerably shorter than the $\text{Al}-\text{C}_b$ bonds (b and t signify bridged and terminal, respectively).

FIGURE 1. The structure of trimethylaluminum.

The structure of the trimethylaluminum dimer has been discussed as if it were static, but that is not the case even at room temperature. When a solution of the compound in toluene is cooled to -65°C , the proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum indicates that there are hydrogen atoms in two types of environments, bridging and terminal methyl groups. However, at room temperature there is only one signal in the NMR spectrum, indicating that the methyl groups exchange. It is believed that the rapid scrambling of methyl groups takes place by breaking one of the bridges followed by rotation of the $\text{Al}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ groups relative to each other with the bridge being reestablished to a different methyl group.

Measurements of the molecular weights in benzene solutions indicate that the methyl, ethyl, and n-propyl compounds are completely dimerized. However, the heat of dissociation of $(\text{AlR}_3)_2$ dimers varies with nature of the alkyl group as shown by the following heats of dissociation:

$R=$	CH_3	C_2H_5	$n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$	$n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$	$i\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$
$\Delta H_{\text{diss}}, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	81.2	70.7	87.4	38	33

Dimethylberyllium

The structure of dimethylberyllium is similar to that of trimethylaluminum except for the fact that the beryllium compound forms chains, whereas the aluminum compound forms dimers. Dimethylberyllium has the structure shown in Figure 1. The bridges involve an orbital on the methyl groups overlapping an orbital (probably best regarded as sp^3) on the beryllium atoms to give two-electron three-center bonds. Note, however, that the bond angle Be-C-Be is unusually small. Because beryllium is a Lewis acid, the polymeric $[\text{Be}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_n$ is separated when a Lewis base is added and adducts form. For example, with phosphine the reaction is

FIGURE 1 The structure of dimethylberyllium.

Polymerization of alkenes by the Ziegler-Natta process

The most important reaction of aluminum alkyls is in polymerization of alkenes by the Ziegler-Natta process. In that process, $\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ reacts as alkylating agent with TiCl_4 , which then undergoes a reaction in which an alkene molecule is inserted in the bond between Ti and the ethyl group, thus lengthening the chain. Because polymers such as polyethylene and polypropylene are produced in enormous quantities and have many important uses, the Ziegler-Natta process has great industrial significance.

The polymerization of alkenes is one of the important processes in which coordination chemistry is involved in what is known as the Ziegler-Natta process. Although polymerization of ethylene can be carried out at high temperature and pressure, a process by which this could be accomplished at room temperature and atmospheric pressure was discovered by **Karl Ziegler in 1952**. The process utilized TiCl_4 and $\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ in a hydrocarbon solvent. It was later found by Giulio Natta that by using other catalyst combinations, polymers having stereoregularity could be produced. Ziegler and Natta shared the 1963 Nobel Prize for their enormously important work. The polymerization reaction can be carried out using other combinations of a **metal halide and a metal alkyl**. Generally, a halide of **titanium, vanadium, or chromium** is used in combination with an **alkyl of beryllium, aluminum, or lithium**. Although the details of the process are not completely understood, the mechanism involves the replacement of a chloride ion by an ethyl group or an ethyl group attaching at a vacant site as the initial step. After a molecule of ethylene is coordinated to the titanium, **it undergoes migration and insertion in the bond between Ti and C_2H_5** . Another ethylene molecule becomes coordinated at the vacant site in the coordination sphere of the Ti, and another insertion reaction occurs, which lengthens the chain, and so on. The reaction scheme shown in **Figure 1** illustrates this process. The crucial step in the process is the insertion reaction by which the hydrocarbon chain is lengthened.

FIGURE 1 The catalytic scheme for polymerization by the Ziegler-Natta process.

Grignard reagents

One of the most important discoveries in organometallic chemistry is that made in **1900 by Victor Grignard**. That work is of enormous importance because it led to the chemistry of a class of compounds that are now referred to as Grignard reagents, and they are prepared by the reaction of **magnesium with an alkyl halide in a solution of dry ether**. The process can be represented by the equation

Evaporation of the excess ether results in the formation of an “etherate” containing the solvent bonded to the magnesium. Generally, the formula for this product is represented as **RMgX₂·2R₂O**, and the structure is a **distorted tetrahedron**. However, even in solution “**RMgX**” exists as **aggregates with the dimer** being the dominant species. The equilibrium

can involve other species, and the composition depends on the nature of the alkyl group, which can function as an electron pair donor; the association is hindered by complex formation between the solvent and RMgX. Moreover, the situation is complicated by the equilibrium

which is known as the **Schlenk equilibrium**. The dimer, (RMgX)₂, is believed to have a structure that can be shown as

although the dimer can also be represented by the structure

There may also be some ionization that can be represented as

The nature of the species present in a solution of a Grignard reagent is a complex issue with no single representation showing the true situation.

Because of the enormous importance of Grignard reagents in synthetic chemistry (organic, inorganic, and organometallic), an entire volume could be written on the subject. Normally, the reactivity of Grignard reagents varies with the nature of the halogen as follows: I > Br > Cl. It is also found that the alkyl compounds are more reactive than the aryl compounds. One of the important types of reactions of Grignard reagents is that of lengthening a carbon chain in the reaction with a primary alcohol.

A concise description of the situation prevailing in solution is given by the Schlenk equilibrium

L = solvent molecule with donor properties, usually ether

$K = 0.2$ for EtMgBr (Equilibrium constant)

An equimolar solution of MgX_2 and R_2Mg in ether behaves identically to a conventional Grignard reagent RMgX . At room temperature, only one signal is observed for the methyl protons, attesting to rapid exchange of CH_3 between CH_3MgBr and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Mg}$. Separate signals appear at $T < -100^\circ\text{C}$ (slow exchange).

The detailed study of the influence of solvent, concentration and the nature of R has revealed that the reality must be more complicated than the description given by the Schlenk equilibrium. In THF, RMgX exists as the monomeric species $\text{RMgX}(\text{THF})_2$ over a wide range of concentrations. In Et_2O , however, RMgX is monomeric only in dilute solution ($< 0.1\text{M}$) whereas at higher concentrations oligomers (chains and rings) are formed:

In general, **halide bridges are preferred over alkyl (2e 3c) bridges**. In the case of $t\text{-BuMgX}$, only monomeric and dimeric units are encountered.

Solutions of RMgX in Et_2O show electrical conductivity, although the extent of dissociation is small:

Ferrocene: Preparation and reactions (acetylation, alkylation, metallation, Mannich condensation). Structure and aromaticity. Comparison of aromaticity and reactivity with that of benzene.

Ferrocene was first produced in 1951, and it quickly became the focus of a great deal of organometallic chemistry. Ferrocene is more correctly named as bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)iron(II), and the molecule has a structure that can be shown as follows:

This structure has been referred to as a “sandwich” structure. At low temperature in the solid state, the rings have the orientation shown, in which they have a **staggered configuration**. However, the rotational barrier is very small, so there is free rotation in the absence of crystal packing that hinders rotation. The fact that there is free rotation has been demonstrated by preparing the derivatives having one substituent on each ring and finding that only one product is obtained. If the molecule were “locked” in the staggered configuration, there would be three possible products having the structures shown in Figure 1

FIGURE 1 The products that should exist if ferrocene were prevented from having free rotation.

In ferrocene and similar complexes, the C_5H_5^- ion behaves as an **aromatic electron donor**. In order for an organic ring structure to achieve **aromaticity**, there must be 2, 6, or 10 electrons to form the π **electron** system ($4n+2$ where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). Benzene is aromatic and forms complexes in which it behaves as if there were three double bonds that donate a total of six electrons. For cyclopentadiene, aromaticity is achieved when there is **one additional electron as is the case in the anion, C_5H_5^-** . Formally, in ferrocene the ligands are considered as negative ions and the **iron as Fe^{2+}** . The Fe^{2+} has 24 electrons, and each ligand behaves as a donor of 6 electrons to Fe^{2+} , giving a total of 36 electrons around Fe in accord with the **18-electron rule**. If the iron were Fe^0 and each ligand were a donor of five electrons, the same total number of electrons around iron would result.

In ferrocene, the cyclopentadiene is bonded by the complete π system to the iron and, therefore, is η^5 - C_5H_5 . In other cases, C_5H_5^- can bind to metals using a localized σ bond, so it is bonded as η^1 . A compound of this type is $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, which has the structure

Preparation of Ferrocene

Hydrogen atoms on the cyclopentadiene ring are very slightly acidic. Therefore, metallic sodium reacts with a solution of cyclopentadiene dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (THF) to liberate hydrogen, leaving sodium cyclopentadienide in solution.

The reaction of this product with FeCl_2 , which can be shown as

When a solution of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is added to a basic solution of cyclopentadiene, the following reaction occurs

Reaction of Ferrocene

Like benzene, the rings in ferrocene are aromatic and undergo electrophilic substitution reactions. Ferrocene undergoes electrophilic substitution reactions more faster than benzene indicating that electrons of Cp ring are more readily available.

Acetylation

Acylation can be carried out by means of a Friedel-Crafts reaction,

Although the disubstituted product is shown in the foregoing equation, some monosubstituted product is also obtained. In this process, AlCl_3 may react with CH_3COCl to generate the $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{O}^+$ attacking species.

It is also possible to introduce the acetyl group by a reaction with acetic anhydride with phosphoric acid as the catalyst. In this reaction under less strenuous conditions, the dominant product is the monosubstituted derivative.

Friedal-Craft alkylation

Ferrocene undergoes Friedal-Craft alkylation using alkyl halide (RX) and AlCl_3 on one ring to give mono alkyl derivative of ferrocene. The entry of the alkyl group which is the electron releasing group, activates the ring for further electrophilic substitution. Thus, the further electrophilic substitution occurs on the mono substituted ring.

The AlCl_3 catalyst reacts with RX to generate the electrophile R^+ .

Where ever possible, the carbocation will rearrange to form the most stable one in the order of $3^\circ > 2^\circ > 1^\circ$.

By a sequence of reactions, the two cyclopentadienyl rings of ferrocene can be connected.

Metallation

The introduction of a metal into the ring is called a metallation reaction. Metallation reactions of ferrocene are useful for synthesising another derivatives. Some metallation reactions are given below :

Mannich condensation

Dimethylamine and formaldehyde undergo a Mannich reaction with ferrocene to give dimethylaminomethylferrocene.

Mechanism :

This electrophile attacks on the Cp ring to give product.

This product is used for the preparation of many other derivatives.